

Electron Mass in Gravitation and Cosmology

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Abstract

Fluctuations of the quantum vacuum are best understood in terms of virtual particle anti-particle pairs. In the context of the Weinberg formula that relates the mass of a pion to fundamental physical constants such as the gravitational constant and the Hubble constant, we will define the mass of an electron in the same fashion since virtual electron-positron pairs are far more common in the quantum vacuum fluctuations of Quantum Electrodynamics than virtual pion pairs. After redefining the Weinberg formula for electrons instead of pions we will replace the Hubble constant with the more suitable Hubble parameter used in modern times in an attempt to help explain why the zero point energy of the vacuum doesn't cause a much larger value of the cosmological constant.

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Large number formulas pointed out by Dirac [1] have attracted the attention of physicists for almost a century, however none so much as the well-known empirical formula pointed out by Weinberg [2] that relates the mass of pions with certain fundamental physical constants.

$$m_{\pi} = \left(\frac{\hbar^2}{Gc} H_0 \right)^{\frac{1}{3}} \quad (1)$$

where m_{π} is the rest mass of a pion, \hbar is the reduced Planck constant, G is the gravitatonpal constant, c is the speed of light and H_0 is the Hubble constant. This would indicate that there is something special about pions in General Relativity, physical Cosmology and studies of Quantum Gravity which shouldn't be the case as pions are a rather small fraction of the matter-energy content of the universe which should mean that virtual pions in the vacuum are the dominant virtual pairs. According to Quantum Field Theory virtual particles are an inherent part of vacuum fluctuations however it is electron-positron pairs that seem to be dominant not virtual charged pions.

In modern times the Hubble constant is obsolete and the Hubble parameter H is used instead. The Hubble Parameter H is a function of the age of the universe and thus it is not a constant but it varies with cosmological time. This drew many physicists to believe that the gravitational constant and maybe the mass of the pion as well, could vary with time on a cosmological scale. Other physicists believe that the Weinberg formula from equation (1) is a mere coincidence and therefore it has no real physical meaning. We will rewrite the Weinberg formula to prove both these assumptions unfounded by relating the mass of an electron to constants in equation one to replace the pion mass.

In the Standard Model of particle physics the rest energy of an electron is defined by an empirical formula:

$$E_e = \frac{2Ry}{\alpha^2(0)} \quad (2)$$

where $1Ry = 13.6056930099(84)$ eV is the Rydberg unit of energy that is a product of the Planck constant and the speed of light hc multiplied by the Ryberg constant R_{∞} and $\alpha(0)$ is the fine structure constant that has an inverse value of $\alpha^{-1}(0) = 137.035999139(31)$. The Rydberg constant and the fine structure constant are two of the most accurately measured quantities in all of physics which is, along with the g -factor of the electron, a test of extraordinary accuracy of Quantum Electrodynamics. Pions are pseudoscalar mesons that come in three types: two charged pions that are each other's anti-particles and a neutral pion that is its own anti-particle. We will only be dealing with charged pions that are slightly more massive than the neutral one. Rest energy of a charged pion can be defined in a similar manner to equation (2):

$$E_\pi = \frac{4Ry}{\alpha^3(M_\pi)} \quad (3)$$

where $\alpha(M_\pi)$ is the running value of the fine structure constant. Running of the fine structure constant on the momentum/energy scale Q is denoted by $\alpha(Q)$ and it only becomes relevant on the electroweak scale when $\alpha^{-1}(M_Z) = 127.916(15)$ [3]. Having in mind that the mass of a Z boson $M_Z = 91.1876(21)$ GeV towers over that of charged pions, we can safely neglect the running of the fine structure constant in equation (3) without sacrificing too much accuracy as the equation then provides the charged pion rest energy of 140 MeV which is very close to the experimental value. This allows us to define the mass of a charged pion in relation to the electron mass $m_\pi = 2m_e\alpha^{-1}(0)$. Now we can rewrite the Weinberg formula as an empirical formula that relates the electron mass to the fundamental constants from equation (1):

$$m_e = \left(\frac{\alpha^3(0)\hbar^2}{8Gc} H_0 \right)^{\frac{1}{3}} \quad (4)$$

which is far more appropriate than equation (1) as the three quantities, namely the electron mass, the fine structure constant and the gravitational constant are the ones that are hypothesized to vary over cosmological temporal scales [4] as well as the fact that this empirical formula requires large quantities of electrons and virtual electron-positron pairs in the QED vacuum which is true unlike the case for virtual pion pairs as it is in the Weinberg formula from equation (1). As D. Slavkov Hajdukovic points out [5] the right hand side of the Weinberg formula doesn't need to vary with time if we use the modern Hubble parameter H instead of the Hubble constant H_0 :

$$m_e = \left(\frac{\alpha^3(0)\hbar^2}{8Gc} H \left\{ \frac{\Omega_\Lambda}{(\Omega - 1)^{1/2}} \cdot \frac{R_0}{R} \right\} \right)^{\frac{1}{3}} \quad (5)$$

where R is the scale factor in the FRW metric and Ω_Λ is the density parameter for the cosmological constant Λ as a candidate for dark energy. Equation (5) could help answer one of the largest mysteries in physics, namely why doesn't the zero point energy of the vacuum cause a larger cosmological constant [6], [7].

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